

Chemotactic swarming of *C. elegans* as a collective decision-making process

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Abstract. Making decisions is a key feature of both natural and artificial swarms, through which they collectively solve tasks they are presented with. We explore how this process occurs in collectives of the roundworm *C. elegans*, a model organism in biology. Despite possessing 302 neurons, they are able to make decisions and to communicate through the release of pheromones. Moreover, the potential of these animals resides in their genetic tractability, with the modification of their genes leading to the altering of their neural functionality. Based on this, we model and optimise swarms of *C. elegans* through sets of differential equations, allowing them to efficiently swarm towards an attractive target, a process referred to as chemotaxis. In particular, we take into consideration two models: one where self-released pheromone production is enabled, and the other where it is not. Then, we analyse the swarming behaviour of the two models in the presence of two targets containing an attractive odour, thus abstracting the swarming task to a collective decision-making process. Our findings suggest that the presence of pheromones is of paramount importance for the capabilities of the swarm to reliably choose one of the two attractive targets.

Keywords: Decision-Making · Evolutionary Strategy · Partial Differential Equations · *Caenorhabditis Elegans*

1 Introduction

Swarms of natural organisms display collective behaviour as a result of the interactions of the individuals inside the swarm to some external or social stimulus. A plethora of collective behaviours has been observed and analysed both in very small organisms such as colonies of bacteria [14,19] and in bigger animals such as fishes [7,16,2], birds [6], and troops of mammals [17,10]. In this study, we focus on the collective behaviour of *C. elegans*, a 1mm long roundworm, thus characterised by a size in between the microscopic scale of bacteria and the macroscopic scale of mammals, referred to as mesoscale [5]. Despite the simplicity of its fully mapped synaptic connections, featuring only 302 neurons in the hermaphrodite animals [22], the natural *C. elegans* worm displays social behaviour when certain conditions, such as sub-optimal ambient oxygen levels and food scarcity, are met.

Through genetic modifications (i.e., genes editing) which aim at reconfiguring specific neural circuits of the worm, it is possible to alter the natural behaviour of *C. elegans*.

Within the EU funded project BABOTS¹, an interdisciplinary team of scientists exploit the possibility to reprogram the behavioural repertoire of *C. elegans*, in order to induce large groups of worms to display complex collective behaviours. This study contributes to the scientific challenge of the BABOTS project by describing a model that allows identifying mechanisms that underpin complex collective decision making processes in genetically modified *C. elegans* worms.

We are interested in the development of a model for the collective swarming of *C. elegans* towards the chemotactic gradient of an attractive chemical odour placed in a target area distant from where the worms are initially placed. Examples of chemotactic assays can be found in [15,21], where experiments are consistently performed with a relatively low number of worms to shed light on the mechanisms underpinning the individual response to chemical stimuli. Contrary to this type of studies, we are interested in exploring the collective response of a large number of worms to a chemotactic gradient. Authors in [12] performed chemotactic assays with different strains of *C. elegans* obtaining useful insights on the correlation between the proportion of worms that reach the odour source and the total number of worms. Nevertheless, they did not attempt to develop models of this phenomenon.

Models of collective behaviour of *C. elegans* have been developed to look at aggregation [18,3,20] and collective motion [23]. Aggregation guided by local levels of oxygen has been studied in [4] through a Keller-Segel [9] macroscopic model. Authors in [5] model both swarming and aggregation in *C. elegans* in presence of food through a microscopic, agent-based model. In this study, we leverage a macroscopic model from the literature [1] for the aggregation of the worms to self-produced attractive and repulsive pheromones. We adapt it so that only an attractive, non self-produced odour is present at a fixed location at a certain distance from where the worms are initially placed. Moreover, we extend the model so that worms produce attractive and repulsive pheromones in order to assess how this might influence the collective swarming. Within this type of models, where partial differential equations (PDEs) govern the evolution of worm and odour densities, parameters representing the interaction of worms to the chemical and the chemical properties of the gradient play a crucial role in the accuracy and time needed for the worms to succeed in reaching the target area. We are interested in analysing the decision-making capabilities of a swarm of *C. elegans* modeled through the aforementioned macroscopic model.

Motivated by previous work [12,11] where the authors study the chemotaxis of individual *C. elegans* when two odour sources are present, we are interested in the behaviour of a swarm of worms when two odour sources, with distinct chemical properties, are present. Such an experiment would represent a first attempt at modeling the decision-making capabilities of a swarm of *C. elegans*

¹ www.babots.eu

solving a best-of- n problem, where a set of n options, each with an associated quality, is present and the swarm needs to reach a consensus on the best option in terms of quality. In particular, the difficulty of the problem would be given by two main factors, namely the chemical properties of the gradient and the distance at which the gradient is placed with respect to the initial position of the worms. Analysing the influence of these two factors would help in building a decision-making model for the chemotactic swarming of *C. elegans*, which, to the best of our knowledge, has not been yet developed.

2 Model

Chemotaxis, i.e. movement towards a chemical source, of a swarm of *C. elegans* can be described through a reaction-diffusion model, where the evolution of the worm density ρ and of the concentration of attractant u is described by two PDEs, similarly to [1]:

$$\frac{d\rho}{dt} = \nabla \cdot [\sigma \nabla \cdot \rho + \rho \nabla \cdot V] \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{du}{dt} = D \nabla^2 u - \gamma u \quad (2)$$

where

$$V = V(u) = -\beta \log(\alpha + u) \quad (3)$$

is the function describing the potential of the attractant source; σ is the random movement of the worms, D and γ are, respectively, the diffusion coefficient and the decay rate of the attractant. Notably, this model is adapted in such a way that the odour source is not produced nor consumed by the worms and worms respond only to the odour gradient, since we ignore density-induced responses. Thus, this model approximates the ideal behaviour of genetically modified worms such that their response level to an attractant odour is pronounced so strongly, that other factors can be ignored. We believe that accounting for a single stimulus can be biologically justifiable, hence giving a reasonable model for the chemotactic swarming of *C. elegans*. The terms in Equation 1 take into account the diffusion of the worms due to their random movement and their taxis towards the odour source potential, while the terms in Equation 2 model the variation in odour concentration by its diffusion and its evaporation.

Moreover, we are interested in expanding Equations 1, 2 so to also include self-produced attractive and repulsive pheromones. Let u_a, u_r be the concentration of attractive and repulsive pheromone. Then the evolution of pheromone i can be described as in [1]:

$$\frac{du_i}{dt} = D_i \nabla^2 u_i - \gamma_i u_i + s_i \rho \quad (4)$$

where $i \in \{a, r\}$ represents the attractive or repulsive pheromone, γ_i is the evaporation rate, D_i the diffusion constant and s_i the secretion rate. In order

to account for the reaction of the worms to the pheromones, we modify the potential V of Equation 1:

$$V = V(u) + V(u_a) + V(u_r) + V_\rho \quad (5)$$

where $V(u)$ is the same as in Equation 3. The last term of Equation 5 is speculated by the authors in [1] to be a potential created by the worms trying to squeeze themselves as compactly as possible:

$$V_\rho = \sigma_{\text{scale}} \left(1 + \tanh \left(\frac{\rho - \rho_{\text{max}}}{\text{cushion}} \right) \right) \quad (6)$$

We solve these systems of PDEs by means of a finite difference scheme, where the environment is a square with length $l = 0.02\text{m}$ discretised in $N = 512$ cells for each of the two spatial coordinates x, y and with periodic boundary conditions. In particular, we resort to a Euler integration scheme with a time step $dt = 0.01$ and a stopping criterion based on the maximum residual $d\rho_{\text{max}}$ per integration step, with $\epsilon = 10^3 \text{worm}/\text{m}^2$, where the unit of measure is expressed in terms of the number of worms per m^2 , together with a maximum allowed time $t_{\text{max}} = 5000$.

In order to evaluate the performance of a given model, we define a chemotactic index c which is simply given by the sum of worm densities inside the target area divided by the total sum of worm densities:

$$c = \frac{\sum_{i=T_1}^{T_2} \sum_{j=T_1}^{T_2} \rho(i, j)}{\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} \rho(i, j)} \quad (7)$$

where $T_1, T_2 \in [0, N - 1]$ such that $T_1 < T_2$ are the indices of the target area, assumed to be a square.

3 Methods

We begin by defining the initial area where worms are placed as a square of 40×40 cells centered at $(380, 300)$ and the target area, filled with the attractive odour, as a square of 40×40 cells centered at $(256, 256)$. Then, we seek to find the best parameters that optimise the swarming towards the target area, thus we employ an evolutionary strategy (**ES**) which is able to find optimal values for this task. An ES is a type of evolutionary algorithm where the parameter values of a particular solution are evaluated in terms of how well they perform with respect to some metric. In our case, we select the metric defined in Equation 7 as the fitness of a solution. The set of solutions, after evaluation, is sorted, then cross-over and mutation are applied and finally the top- λ solutions are kept for the next generation, while the top- m solutions, called the elites, are always kept. In particular, we leverage the self-adaptative ES (**SA-ES**) as in [8]. All meta-parameters are listed in Table 1. One of the most important aspects of such a strategy is the selection of reasonable bounds for the parameter values: the broader, the less likely the numerical simulation is able to converge; the narrower,

the harder it is to find an optimum. Based on these numerical limitations, we choose to iteratively apply SA-ES, broadening the range of the parameters and augmenting the initial number of solutions until the improvement of the best solution is negligible. We begin by using the values in Table 2 and define the lower (l_i) and upper (u_i) bounds of each parameter i as:

$$l_i = \frac{t_i}{\mu} \quad (8)$$

$$u_i = t_i \mu \quad (9)$$

where t_i is the value of the parameter in Table 2 and μ is an integer. The strategy employs iteratively higher values of μ following an exponential trend where the power is 2 and with an initial value of 2.

Table 1. Meta-parameters for the SA-ES leveraged for the optimisation process as in [8].

Meta-parameter	Value
maximum number of generations	10
population size	10
mutation rate	0.1
elitism	3
minimum number of offspring λ_{min}	2
maximum number of offspring λ_{max}	100
mutation boost factor c	2
memory of previous epochs m	10

4 Results

We first establish a baseline behaviour, where chemotaxis is driven solely by the diffusion of the attractive odour placed in the center of the environment, thus solving Equations 1, 2 with the initial parameters listed in Table 2, with $\rho_0 = 1.2 \times 10^8$. Numerical solutions of ρ without pheromone production are shown in the top row of Figure 1: at $t = 0$ (a), the worms are placed on the initial area; at $t = 2500$ (b) the worms have sensed the diffused odour and begun to aggregate in the target area; finally, at $t = 5000$ (c), the chemotactic index of Equation 7 gives $c \approx 0.52$. This indicates that the worms first diffuse around their initial area, until the odour has diffused enough for them to sense it; then they initiate movement to this source, while still partially diffusing. However, the value reached by the chemotactic index with these parameters is well below any optimum, as they are taken from [1] and represent basic *L1* worms. Since it is possible to genetically alter the synaptic connections of *C. elegans* and thus modify their natural behaviour, we propose to optimise the parameters of

Fig. 1. Heatmap representing the worm density ρ at $t = 0$ (a), $t = 2500$ (b) and $t = 5000$ (c) when an attractive odour is placed in the center of the environment without pheromone release (top) and with pheromones (bottom). Initial worm density: $\rho = 120 \times 10^6$ worm/m². The heatmap is normalised with a logarithmic scale with a cut-off for values below 10^3 .

the models in order to achieve ideal swarming, such that all worms reach the target area. Hence, we can design worms by employing the SA-ES as described in Section 3, which aims at maximising the density in the target area by evolving a population of individuals each possessing a genome composed of the model parameters. The evolved parameters are then fed to the numerical solver and the final relative density in the target area is evaluated. The evolutionary strategy leverages the hyperparameters in Table 1. After two rounds of optimisation, we find a value of $c \approx 0.996$ with the parameters as in Table 2. The latter shows as well the intermediate optimisation step parameter values and its fitness.

The same method is applied to the model featuring the self-produced pheromones composed of Equations 1, 2 and 4, thus with the potential V as in Equation 6. The bottom row of Figure 1 shows the numerical solution of ρ : at $t = 0$ (a) the worms are placed in the initial square; at $t = 2500$ (b) they begin to diffuse and at $t = 5000$ (c) the chemotactic index of Equation 7 has a value of $c \approx 0.63$. When pheromones production is enabled, the worm density visually appears less sparse and results in a higher chemotactic index. We then optimise

Table 2. Initial and optimised parameters in the odour model after one and two rounds of SA-ES. Values are approximated to the second significant digit.

Parameter	Starting Value	First Round Value	Second Round Value	Unit
σ	5.56×10^{-10}	3.35×10^{-10}	2.52×10^{-10}	m^2s^{-1}
γ	1.00×10^{-4}	1.74×10^{-4}	1.40×10^{-4}	s^{-1}
β	1.11×10^{-8}	2.19×10^{-8}	4.39×10^{-8}	m^2s^{-1}
α	1.50×10^6	7.60×10^5	1.25×10^6	m^{-2}
D	1.00×10^{-9}	1.56×10^{-9}	3.16×10^{-9}	m^2s^{-1}
ρ_0	1.2×10^8	1.08×10^8	4.33×10^8	m^{-2}
c	0.52	0.9	0.996	

the pheromone model following the method described in Section 3. The initial and optimised values are reported in Table 3, where the SA-ES is able to find an optimal value of $c = 0.98$ after two rounds of optimisation. Before moving on, we would like to point out that SA-ES has found in the second round of optimisation a solution where the initial worm density ρ_0 is lower than the initial value, contrary to the first round, where it is slightly higher. This means that with a lower initial density, we are able to achieve a higher degree of swarming, which does not seem to be the case when pheromone production is disabled, as per Table 2.

With these parameters, we now seek to assess the performance of the model with and without self-produced pheromones in different environmental setups. First, we begin by fixing two areas of 40×40 cells containing the attractive odour, namely A and B , with the same chemical properties. Target A is centered in the cell $(380, 300)$, while target B is centered at $(b_0, 300)$, with $b_0 \in [20, 256]$. In our experiments, we moved b_0 20 cells at a time. The worms are placed in a 40×40 cells area in the center of the environment $O = (256, 256)$. In particular, we find that the distance of O from the two targets influences the target to where the worms aggregate: if b_0 is placed in such a way that B and A are equidistant from O , then we expect that an equal number of worms will aggregate on each target. In Figure 2 we show the final density distribution when A and B are equidistant from the center, thus with $b_0 = 132$, both with and without pheromones using the starting parameter values. The chemotactic indices of A and B are roughly equal, suggesting that when the distance of the two odour sources is equal, the attraction is equal, thus divides the population in two, as can be seen by the value of c inside the two target areas: $c_A \approx c_B$. Distance is an important factor as well as the diffusion of the chemical odour: this has been studied *in-vitro* in [13], where the authors find that a stronger diffusion constant of the attractive odour is correlated to a stronger chemotactic response. To test this idea, we decided to run numerical simulations across a range of diffusion constants D from 1.12 to $4.47 \times 10^{-9} \text{m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ while varying b_0 as before. This range has been chosen as to accommodate the optima of both the pheromone and the pheromone-deprived models (blue cell in Tables 2 and 3). The key observation is that worms are

Table 3. Initial and optimised parameters in the pheromone model after one and two rounds of SA-ES. Values are approximated to the second significant digit.

Parameter	Starting Value	First Round Value	Second Round Value	Unit
σ	5.56×10^{-10}	1.04×10^{-9}	2.74×10^{-10}	m^2s^{-1}
γ	1.00×10^{-4}	1.38×10^{-4}	8.28×10^{-5}	s^{-1}
β	1.11×10^{-8}	1.83×10^{-8}	2.82×10^{-8}	m^2s^{-1}
α	1.50×10^6	7.60×10^5	1.32×10^6	m^{-2}
D	1.00×10^{-9}	1.83×10^{-9}	2.23×10^{-9}	m^2s^{-1}
ρ_0	1.2×10^8	1.58×10^8	5.54×10^7	m^{-2}
β_a	4.111×10^{-10}	6.59×10^{-10}	2.82×10^{-10}	m^2s^{-1}
α_a	1.5×10^6	1.8×10^6	1.6×10^6	m^{-2}
γ_a	10^{-3}	1.38×10^{-3}	2.7×10^{-3}	s^{-1}
s_a	10^3	5.05×10^2	3.5×10^3	$\text{m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$
D_a	10^{-10}	1.56×10^{-10}	2.7×10^{-10}	m^2s^{-1}
β_r	-1.111×10^{-13}	-9×10^{-13}	-3.1×10^{-12}	m^2s^{-1}
α_r	1.5×10^6	2.87×10^6	3.6×10^6	m^{-2}
γ_r	10^{-3}	1.67×10^{-3}	1.1×10^{-3}	s^{-1}
s_r	10	18.99	22	$\text{m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$
D_r	10^{-10}	1.04×10^{-10}	3.8×10^{-10}	m^2s^{-1}
scale	2	3.21	5.56	
ρ_{max}	2.8×10^8	4.58×10^8	10^9	m^{-2}
cushion	2×10^8	2.95×10^8	6×10^7	m^{-2}
c	0.63	0.85	0.98	

performing a collective decision-making task: their collective swarming towards A or towards B corresponds to them making a decision, and if a sufficient number of them reaches one of the two targets, we can say that they have decided that to be the best target. In particular, this resembles a best-of-2 problem, where the swarm is presented with two options and they need to agree on the best option in terms of its quality. Imposing the distances from O and the diffusion constants of A and B to be equal, we incur in a symmetry breaking problem, since these two properties can represent the quality of the two options. Hence, we arbitrarily impose a quorum $\theta = 0.7$, which represents the minimum relative density ρ in either of the two spots, which is equivalent to the metric in Equation 7 applied to target A (c_A) and B (c_B), such that a decision has been made. In other words, when $c_A > \theta$, a decision has been made for option A , while when $c_B > \theta$, a decision has been made for option B . When neither of these conditions is met, we define the outcome of the decision-making process as a decision deadlock.

Figure 3 shows the phase separation diagram for the decision-making process initiated by the swarming of the simulated worm densities when pheromone production is disabled (Fig 3a) and when it is enabled (Fig 3b). The blue region corresponds to an agreement on option A ($c_A > \theta$), while the green region corresponds to an agreement on option B ($c_B > \theta$). The yellow region corresponds

Fig. 2. Heatmap representing the worm density ρ at $t = 5000$ when an attractive odour is placed in two square spots equidistant from the center, where the worms are initially placed, without pheromone release (a) and with pheromones (b). In (a) $c_A = 0.40$ and $c_B = 0.37$, while in (b) $c_A = 0.45$ and $c_B = 0.41$. Initial worm density: $\rho = 120 \times 10^6$ worm/m². The heatmap is normalised with a logarithmic scale with a cut-off for values below 10^3 .

to a decision deadlock. We can observe that when B is equidistant from A , since the two spots have the same chemical properties, neither the pheromone-enabled nor the pheromone-deprived system is able to break the symmetry. This is in line with *in-vitro* results from [12], where the authors find that in the presence of two attractive sources placed at the same distance from the initial position of the worms, the chemotactic index is fixed at around 0.5 (Figure 6B, right panel). In the case of B being closer to the origin than A (lower half of Figure 3), there tends to be an agreement on B , while the opposite is true for the case of A being closer to the origin than B (upper half of Figure 3). Indeed, distance is a key factor influencing the chemotactic preference of optimised *C. elegans* since the odour that is able to reach them faster will be targeted by a greater proportion of worms. This concept can also be seen by the tendency to incur in a decision deadlock when the diffusion constant of both odours increases, leading more frequently to a deadlock. In particular, the proportion of points resulting in a deadlock for Figure 3a is 45.83%, while for Figure 3b it is 28.33%. The overall lower deadlock proportion suggests that the presence of pheromones contributes greatly to the symmetry-breaking capabilities of the swarm.

Figure 4 shows the phase separation diagram for the decision-making process when target A has a fixed position and a fixed diffusion constant, while the position and diffusion constant of B are varied. In particular, Figure 4a corre-

Fig. 3. Phase separation diagrams for the decision-making process when two equivalent odour sources are present, namely A , whose position is fixed, and B , whose position is varied, without (a) and with pheromones (b). Each cell in the grid represents the numerical integration of the corresponding system (with/without pheromones), with a specific diffusion constant of the odour and a distance of B from the center in units each of length $\frac{l}{N}$. Regions in blue correspond to $c_A > \theta$, while regions in green correspond to $c_B > \theta$ and the regions in yellow to a decision deadlock.

sponds to the case when no pheromones are produced and Figure 4b to the case when pheromones are produced. For both cases, a vertical line shows the corresponding value for the diffusion constant of A , as per Tables 2 and 3. We can observe that when the diffusion constant of B is close to the diffusion constant of A (D_A), both phase separation diagrams around the vertical line of Figure 4 resemble the corresponding phase diagram of Figure 3. For example, the diagram in Figure 4a around D_A shows a decision has been made for the target that is closer to the center, with some deadlocks due to the relatively high diffusion constant, while it incurs in a deadlock when the two targets are equidistant from the center. These observations are consistent with those for the diagram in Figure 3a. Analogous observations can be made for the case when pheromones are present (Figures 4b, 4b). Moreover, we notice that pheromone production is disabled, the decision for A is made mostly when A is closer to the origin than B , while the decision for B is located in a region following a linear trend between the distance of B from the origin and its diffusion constant. The proportion of points resulting in a decision deadlock is 45.83% when no pheromones are

Fig. 4. Phase separation diagrams for the decision-making process when two odour sources are present, namely A , whose position and diffusion constant (D_A) are fixed, and B , whose position and diffusion constant are varied, without (a) and with pheromones (b). Each cell in the grid represents the numerical integration of the corresponding system, with a specific diffusion constant of the odour and a distance of B from the center in units each of length $\frac{l}{N}$. Regions in blue correspond to $c_A > \theta$, while regions in red correspond to $c_B > \theta$ and the regions in yellow to a decision deadlock.

present and 20.0% when pheromones are present. The case with pheromones has the same trends, however it features a lower deadlock area, reinforcing the suggestion that pheromones play a crucial role in the symmetry-breaking properties of the system.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we demonstrate how the swarming guided by chemotaxis of *C. elegans* resembles a collective decision-making process in the best-of- n problem. We consider a macroscopic Keller-Segel model from the literature [1] which we modify to account for the presence of one or more attractive odours and which allows the worms to produce attractive and repulsive pheromones. We thus consider two cases: when the only source of attraction is given by the attractive source(s) and when pheromone production is enabled as well. The parameters governing the models with and without pheromones are optimised through an evolutionary strategy with respect to the same swarming task, where our desired

behaviour is for all the worms to reach the designated target area, containing the attractive odour. Then, those parameters are used to test the ability of the swarm in making a decision within a best-of-2 problem. In particular, the two options are given by two target areas each containing an odour source, namely A and B . In a first experiment we vary the distance of target B from the origin, while keeping the distance of A fixed. Furthermore, we designed an experiment where in addition to the position, we also fix the diffusion constant of A and vary both the distance and the diffusion constant of B . The resulting worm densities were then categorised into outcomes favoring target A or B , where a given quorum is able to reach one of the two targets, and the inability to favour either, which we define as a decision deadlock. Our findings imply that the presence of self-produced pheromones plays a pivotal role in the capabilities of the swarm to break decision deadlocks. This difference can be explained by the biological phenomenon that made the worms evolve to display pheromones: as in any organism, communication between organisms is an important factor regulating the way they behave. Through the optimisation of the parameters representing the properties of these chemicals, we show that this type of communication, a type of stigmergy, allows worms to choose an odour source over another one more robustly. Future work should be devoted to a more accurate analysis of the two different types of behaviours: from a preliminary analysis we find that in the model without pheromones, worms are able to reach the desired quorum faster than the model with pheromones, although the latter is able to perform better in terms of symmetry-breaking. This leads to the conclusion that a trade-off between speed and accuracy exists even in swarms of *C. elegans*. One possible direction for future work could be the analysis of heterogeneous swarms, composed of both worms that produce pheromones and of worms that do not. However, the current model may be inadequate for such a task given the ever-increasing amount of equations that are needed to be solved. Hence, it would be more adequate to move to an agent-based model, leveraging parallelisation and allowing for different parameter values within the same simulation.

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